

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING GEOGRAPHY TO STUDENTS IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12530739>

Abstract: This article considers the main problems related to the organization of the educational process, taking into account the peculiarities of teaching geography and the characteristics of children's perception of the world around them. Methodical methods of using visual aids in geography lessons for children with disabilities are analyzed, the experience of working with didactic material is described.

Key words: Inclusive education, individual education, geographical methods, modern methods, pedagogical innovations, training manuals, handouts, action and visual games. Working with maps.

The practice of inclusive education is based on the idea of accepting the individuality of each student, and therefore education should create a corrective environment in such a way as to meet the special needs of each child. Development and correction of intellectual activity of students with disabilities is considered in geography lessons. In organizing geography classes, the skills of the pedagogue are in the first place to ensure the education of students with disabilities. A teacher who teaches children with disabilities inevitably faces a number of problems. For example, how to ensure the success of every student in learning, how to maintain and strengthen the child's health while organizing educational activities.

Teaching disabled children will be effective if the following pedagogical conditions are met:

- use of customized educational programs and training manuals;
- drawing up work programs and lesson notes that contribute to their comprehensive development, taking into account the characteristics of the psychophysical development of disabled students;
- application of an individual approach, taking into account the emotional and volitional sphere, a person-oriented and differential approach;
- exchange of mental and practical activities, use of interesting and colorful didactic materials and visual aids;
- use of changing activities during training (physical education and other interesting activities);

Using methods that activate students' cognitive activity and cognitive interest in the subject of "Geography";

- constant monitoring of homework completion (necessary volume, compliance with the given material);
- unity and consistency of requirements for students with disabilities.

The main goal of today's pedagogue should be the use of active teaching methods, games and information and communication technologies when conducting geography lessons. Multimedia presentations, educational and documentary films, as well as various didactic materials should be widely used in the educational process. Textbook and workbook are the main teaching tools, which are actively used in every lesson. During the lesson, students work with textbook materials, a colorful appendix to the textbook, and after studying the topic, they should be asked to test their knowledge with questions after the paragraphs or tasks in the workbook.

The set of lessons conducted on the formation of cognitive interest in geography includes:

- the use of a large number of game methods and forms. For example, exercise games last about 10 minutes and are aimed at improving the cognitive abilities of children with disabilities, and are also a good way to develop cognitive interests, understand and reinforce the lesson material.

"Hatching" exercise. In this exercise, a contour map divides the continents in different ways. This exercise is aimed at developing and correcting coordinated movements of visual and motor analyzers.

"Identify by outline" exercise. In this exercise, children are asked to recognize the continents by their contours, the task can be complicated by turning the images of the continents upside down. Physical exercises help to develop visual perception, memory and attention.

Exercise "Color program" (for individual work). The child is given 6 color images of the continents, he must place the maps on the world map. The exercise develops the ability to move the eye in space and perceive areas.

"Geographic alphabet" exercise. The task is to list the terms in alphabetical order. The task is performed orally or in writing, face-to-face or individually, within a certain time.

"Geographic crossword" exercise. Any crossword is useful to enrich our vocabulary. These exercises are suitable for school-aged students, and it was considered very important to use crosswords for students of different ages. Students perceive such geographical tasks as different games. They always play

games like this with pleasure. Observing the learning process shows that students effectively perform these exercise tasks even at the end of the lesson when they run out of learning opportunities. Some geographical exercises help to improve the creative literacy of students. For example, tasks that require geographic schematic drawings. This greatly facilitates the work of students who have difficulty expressing their thoughts or answers verbally.

There are also additional geographic tasks to develop the scientific skills of students with disabilities. For example, working with the plasticine method. A model of a mountain range is made from plasticine. Its parts are marked with symbols, or a volcano model is made from plasticine. Such activities train concentration, hard work, develop perception and increase interest in geography. In raising and teaching children with disabilities, the teacher should not only impart knowledge, but also develop the ability to think independently.

During extracurricular hours, we can use the following board games for individual work to develop worldview, color perception, logical thinking and fine motor skills of students with disabilities:

Note "Monuments of the World". Each card in the collection contains famous architectural monuments of the world. The set includes a booklet describing all the locations shown on the cards.

World Map Puzzle is a puzzle game where the child has to create a picture from a large number of pieces.

Magical Geography is a game guide that can be used to explore the geography and habitats of fauna around the world. The game manual has many stickers that can be applied and removed many times without leaving any marks. Each sticker can then be examined individually, explaining which part of the Earth and climate is best suited for that animal and why. Visualization is a tool that helps to implement the process of inclusive education. Images attract students' attention, arouse their emotions, and help them remember the material. Inclusive education in geography is a process of education and upbringing in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other characteristics, are included in the general education system and receive education in their place of residence together with their peers with disabilities. . They are general educational institutions that take into account their special educational needs and provide the necessary specialist support. Inclusive education involves the involvement of children with different disabilities in the educational process and educational institutions create appropriate conditions for this. Geographic infographics are an old-fashioned reference point, so time-

tested techniques can work well in modern settings. An infographic is not just something created on a computer, but organized information and its graphic representation. You can also create infographics by drawing on paper or whiteboard by hand or on computer. Each teacher plans his activities independently: chooses interesting, convenient, personal and practice-oriented content. Uses various manuals and technical means to achieve goals. Organizes various activities for children, including creative activities related to various types of art, excursions, didactic games, etc.

The practice of inclusive education is based on the idea of accepting the individuality of each student, and therefore, education should be organized in such a way as to meet the special needs of each child, by organizing a correctional space. Development and correction of intellectual activity of students with disabilities is considered in geography lessons.

Education in many ways determines a person's life, his well-being, success and the possibility of self-realization. Prospects of social development in the modern world mainly depend on the state of the education system, its ability to meet the needs of individuals and society for high-quality educational services. Psychological-pedagogical thought is increasingly addressing the problems of person-oriented education. Teachers are increasingly interested in personality development and internal mechanisms of self-development. A child is not only an object of external influence, but also a subject of his own life. The object of influence should not be the student himself with his special inner world, but the conditions under which he grows up and builds himself as a person. The fact is that the modern school is not able to take into account the psychophysiological characteristics of the child, to build an individual trajectory of his development on this basis, to create conditions for the maximum realization of the individual, both with gifted children and with gifted children.

While working on the problem of activation of cognitive activity in geography classes, tasks are set to make educational activities interesting, to make difficult material understandable and simple for students, and to make lessons more interesting. The introduction of non-traditional methods and forms of teaching at different stages of the lesson helped to solve these problems. In geography classes, it is important to improve the environment of interest in knowledge, research, creation, and the desire to develop intelligence. Therefore, it is necessary to look for different ways and methods of supporting students' cognitive interests in any type of cognitive activity, in any direction.

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